

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYETHYLENE FIBRE/CARBON FIBRE HYBRID LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Interlaminar hybrid laminates reinforced with a high modulus, high energy absorption polyethylene fibre (Spectra 900) and a carbon fibre (AS4) have been tested in flexure, interlaminar shear, and drop weight impact. The measured properties vary as a function of the ratio of the two types of plies and as a function of the laminate stacking sequence. In impact, an increasing amount of polyethylene fibre leads to large improvements in impact resistance, but at the expense of a lower interlaminar shear strength. In flexure, the laminate stiffness improves with increasing number of carbon fibre plies, especially when these layers are on the outside, but at the expense of a lower strain to failure. It is suggested that all the measured properties are related, and it should be possible to tailor laminates for specific applications

INTRODUCTION

Recently data on the mechanical properties of a new generation of very high modulus polyethylene fibres have been presented in the literature [1,2]. These new fibres, which are produced by different methods by at least two manufacturers, have mechanical properties which are significantly different from conventional carbon, glass or aramid fibres.

Laminates made with these new fibres have excellent impact properties and strain to failure, good tensile moduli and strengths, and are of low density, but suffer from low transverse, shear, and compressive properties.

As a result, though all-polyethylene fibre reinforced composites may be difficult to use in some load-bearing applications, hybridization with carbon or glass fibres has become an area of great interest [3,4]. The potential is significant: at one extreme, the addition of some polyethylene fibre to a carbon reinforced laminate may enhance poor impact resistance, whilst at the other extreme, addition of some carbon or glass fibre to a polyethylene fibre reinforced laminate may provide needed compressive or shear properties.

The results presented in this work are the first part of a systematic study of the hybridization of one polyethylene fibre, **SPECTRA-900**, manufactured by the Allied Signal Corporation.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

(1) Flexure Tests (ASTM D790)

To evaluate the static properties of unidirectional interlaminar twelve-ply hybrids the 3-pt flexure test was chosen in preference to the tension test, where thick polyethylene fibre-based laminates are susceptible to grip failure. The length to thickness ratio was sufficiently large (≈ 50 in most cases) such that shear deformations were negligible [5]. Flexural modulus, outer fibre stress and strain at failure were recorded. All tests were performed on an Instron screw-driven testing machine at a crosshead speed of 6-8 mm/min. Specimens were 88-110 mm long and 25 mm wide, with thicknesses in the range 1.45 mm to 1.85 mm. The span distance varied between 73 and 93 mm.

(2) Interlaminar Shear Strength Tests (ASTM D2344)

The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) test is a popular measure of the degree of internal bonding of a laminate. The low ILSS value of polyethylene composites has been generally considered to be a drawback. As such, one goal of the hybridization program has been to improve the ILSS.

As defined in the ASTM standard, the test is valid only for unidirectional layups of one material, and even then there is reason to suspect the validity of the results [6]. This limitation arises from the analysis, which assumes that failure occurs at the midplane of the laminate where the shear stress distribution is at a maximum. In an interlaminar hybrid laminate this is not always the case. Using a more sophisticated analysis [7], the shear (and in-plane) stress distribution through the thickness can be determined for any lay-up (for example, see Figure 1). Even if the shear stress is a maximum at the mid-plane, failure may occur at another interface where the strength is lower. As a result, it is possible to obtain an ILSS value, as defined by the standard, that is different in magnitude from the shear stress at the failing interface. However, this **apparent ILSS** is useful in that it is a measure of the interlaminar shear strength of the hybrid **as a structure**. Tests were performed at a crosshead speed of 1.3 mm/min, with a span to depth ratio of 5.

(3) Drop Weight Impact Test (ASTM D3029)

The Drop Weight Impact Test was chosen in preference to Charpy-type tests since it is believed to give a more realistic assessment of impact properties. 127 mm square panels were clamped between plates with a 76 mm circular cutout. The panels were clamped since experience has shown that polyethylene fibre laminates have sufficient ductility that they will be pulled through the orifice without penetration of the panel. The crosshead mass was 9.9 kg, with an impact velocity of 3.9 m/s. Panel thicknesses were in the range 1.1 to 2.2 mm. The 12.7 mm diameter tup was instrumented, and a high speed digital oscilloscope captured the load-time curve. The trace was then analysed and peak load, energy to peak load, and total energy absorbed evaluated.

Figure 1. Schematic distributions of stresses in a laminate in flexure

Figure 2. Flexural modulus of unidirectional hybrid laminates as a function of stacking sequence

Figure 3. Outer fibre strain at failure in unidirectional hybrid laminates as a function of stacking sequence

Figure 4. Outer fibre stress at failure in unidirectional hybrid laminates as a function of stacking sequence

FABRICATION

Pre-impregnated sheets of carbon fibre (Hercules **AS4**) and polyethylene fibre (Allied Signal **SPECTRA-900**, corona surface treated) respectively, were made on a drum type winder using either a **Derekane 411-45** vinyl-ester or an **Epon 826** epoxy as matrix material. After cutting and laying up of the required interlaminar hybrid sequence, the laminates were cured in an autoclave for 3 hours at 38 or 65 °C depending on the resin, followed by a post-cure of 3 days at 60-70 °C. Typical total fibre volume fractions were about 55%, with the ratio of the two fibres determined by the stacking sequence. Note that the two material thicknesses are different, so that a hybrid with an equal number of layers of carbon and polyethylene does not have equal volume fractions. Unless otherwise stated, the results in this work refer to the vinyl-ester based laminates.

Two laminate configurations were used. The samples for flexural tests were unidirectional 12-ply laminates, whilst the impact panels were 9-ply cross-ply lay-ups. ILSS tests were performed for all panels.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(1) Flexural Tests

Eight unidirectional arrangements were tested: namely $[S_{12}]_T$, $[C_2/S_4]_S$, $[S_4/C_2]_S$, $[C_3/S_3]_S$, $[S_3/C_3]_S$, $[C_4/S_2]_S$, $[S_2/C_4]_S$, $[C_{12}]_T$. Average results from five specimens are shown in bar chart form in Figures 2,3,4 for the flexural stiffness, outer fibre strain at failure, and the outer fibre stress at failure respectively.

Figure 2 shows clearly the benefit of having the carbon layers as far from the mid-plane as possible, so that their moment of inertia is greatest. This benefit is balanced by a significantly lower outer fibre strain to failure when the carbon layers are on the outside (Figure 3). Figure 4 shows the variation of the outer fibre stress at failure, and here the trend is more difficult to discern. Increasing carbon content improves the stiffness, but this gain is counteracted by a lower strain to failure (approximately 1.4% cf 3.3%).

The trend for flexural moduli is even clearer if we plot the results as a function of the fraction of the total fibre volume that is polyethylene. Results lie on two curves, one for carbon on the outside, and the other for polyethylene on the outside. Note that two parameters are changing simultaneously, namely the relative amount of fibres, and the thickness and position of the layers. As such, a linear relation should not be expected in Figure 5.

The ILSS is shown as a function of the fraction of polyethylene fibre in Figure 6. The hybrid values vary between the limits of the all carbon and the all polyethylene laminates though the relationship is predicted to be more complicated than a linear correlation.

It is instructive to cross-plot the flexural modulus against the ILSS (Figure 7). Again, the results lie on two curves. However, it now becomes clear that it is not possible to maximize both ILSS and flexural modulus at the same time in an efficient manner. Though both values increase with increasing carbon content, the ILSS is maximized most efficiently when the carbon is at the midplane, whilst the flexural modulus benefits most when the carbon is at the outer faces. This type of trade-off is even more pronounced when the impact results are discussed in the next section.

Figure 5. Flexural modulus as a function of the fraction of the total fibre volume that is polyethylene fibre

Figure 6. Apparent interlaminar shear strength as a function of the fraction of the total fibre volume that is polyethylene fibre

Figure 7. Variation of the flexural modulus with the apparent interlaminar shear strength

Figure 8. Density as a function of the fraction of the total fibre volume that is polyethylene fibre

All the values reported in this work are absolute values. In many weight sensitive applications, the specific properties are of greater interest. Figure 8 shows the variation of the panel density as a function of fraction of polyethylene fibre. The density decreases in an essentially linear fashion by over 30%, as the layup is varied from all carbon to all polyethylene.

(2) Drop Weight Impact Tests

Results from the impact tests are shown in Figures 9,10, and 11 respectively for energy absorbed to peak load, total energy absorbed, and peak load, as a function of volume fraction of polyethylene fibre in the laminate. The filled symbols refer to all polyethylene reinforced laminates.

The trend in all three parameters is similar. With increasing polyethylene fibre content, the energies (both peak and total) and the peak load increase. There is considerable scatter in the results, though it must be noted that each point corresponds to an individual panel. Part of the variation in the results is due to the different stacking sequences in the hybrids (even though the volume fractions might be similar), and other effects discussed below.

The results presented in the figures may be compared to slightly thicker cross-ply panels of glass and aramid fibre tested in Reference [8]. For glass/epoxy the values are 7192 N, 35.4 J, 46.8 J; for aramid/epoxy the values are 3150 N, 14.7 J, 21.8 J for peak load, energy to peak load, and total energy absorbed respectively. The densities are 1.93 and 1.46 respectively. It can be seen that the all-polyethylene laminates are nearly as good as glass reinforced laminates, whilst many of the hybrids are superior to the aramid. In terms of specific properties, the polyethylene and hybrid reinforcement become even more attractive.

A significant difference between the all-polyethylene and polyethylene-rich hybrids on one side, and all the other laminates on the other, is the appearance of the impact damage zone. The major mechanism for energy absorption by the polyethylene fibre appears to be the deformation of the fibre itself. Those panels which show high energy absorption have a large dished impact zone, with a great deal of permanent deformation prior to failure. Those panels which absorb marginally more energy than the all carbon reinforced panels show a localised damage zone, where the tup has simply penetrated the panel. In the latter case a large part of the energy absorption goes into breaking through. This effect can also be observed in Figure 12, where the ductility index (=energy absorbed after peak load/energy absorbed before peak load) decreases from a large value (which indicates more energy absorbed after peak load) to practically zero (which indicates practically no energy absorbed after peak load).

These results lead to the observation that if the damage zone is constrained by any means, then the energy absorbed will decrease, well beyond what a rule of mixtures approach would suggest. For example, if the interlaminar shear strength of the **hybrid structure** increases, then the ability to deform grossly is inhibited and we would expect the energy parameters to decrease. This is shown in Figure 13, where the energy absorbed to peak load drops by more than a factor of four as the ILSS increases. Thus it appears that a relatively low ILSS value may be necessary for good impact properties. However, a low ILSS is not sufficient in itself: a high strain to failure fibre capable of deforming and absorbing energy is required.

Further variables that will influence the behaviour of the hybrid include the stacking sequence, where any arrangement that serves to stiffen the panel may lead to a smaller damage zone, as the tup will find it easier to punch through rather than deform the bulk of the panel. Finally, it is important to note that the drop

Figure 9. Energy absorbed to peak load in a drop weight impact test as a function of the polyethylene fibre volume fraction

Figure 10. Total energy absorbed in a drop weight impact test as a function of the polyethylene fibre volume fraction

Figure 11. Peak load measured in a drop weight impact test as a function of the polyethylene fibre volume fraction

Figure 12. Ductility Index (=energy absorbed after peak load/energy absorbed before peak load in a drop weight impact test) as a function of the polyethylene fibre volume fraction

Figure 13. Energy absorbed to peak load in a drop weight impact test as a function of the apparent interlaminar shear strength of the laminate.

Figure 14. Variation of energy absorbed to peak load in a drop weight impact test with specimen thickness

weight impact test itself may be misleading. As mentioned above, any effect that serves to stiffen the panel may localise the damage; thus the thickness of the panels may have an effect. Figure 14 shows the reduction in energy absorbed to peak load in the hybrid configurations as a function of laminate thickness. Though there are not enough results for any conclusive observations, it appears that the panel thickness may have a large effect, especially on systems that are capable of large deformations. If this is correct, it will prove very difficult to compare results with other workers, and even more difficult to extrapolate laboratory results to real structures.

CONCLUSIONS

Results from a wide range of unidirectional and cross-ply interlaminar hybrid laminates made of polyethylene fibres (**SPECTRA-900**) and carbon fibres (**AS4**) show that the hybrid properties vary as a function of relative volume fractions of the fibres and stacking sequence. In the case of static properties, an increasing carbon content is desirable, whilst the impact properties are enhanced by increasing the polyethylene content. There is a trade-off between the properties, and any one property can be maximized, whilst minimizing the losses in other properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The technical assistance of Mr. J. Arblaster, Mr. R. Bennett, and Mr. M. Dorosh is much appreciated. The authors are grateful for financial support by Allied Signal Canada, and the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada.

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